

TEXT ON WORK INTO THE VIRTUAL WORLD THROUGH TRAVEL

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Abstract

This article provides recommendations on how to teach students to think independently and creatively through the virtual world, develop their learning activities, and develop their speech by attracting students to literature. The processes of organizing literary trips through the virtual environment, showing film clips, and analyzing the content of the work through storytelling, and the formation of rapid, expressive reading skills are taken into account.

Keywords: Virtual world, text, fiction, speech development, literary journey, excursion, synthesis.

In today's globalization process, the integration of information and communication technologies into the educational process creates new opportunities, but it is natural that it also places great responsibility on the shoulders of teachers. To interest students in literature, they can be interested in it through direct work on the text and travel to the virtual world. Working on the text in the virtual world is very useful for students. This approach not only instills in them a love for literature, but also helps them develop independent thinking and creativity. Interactive tools and technologies in the virtual world create new opportunities for students to better master the text and analyze it. For example, in a virtual environment, the reading process can be made more interesting and effective by analyzing the text, discussing what has been read, and using various visual and audiovisual materials. This in turn students analysis to do, understand and create skills strengthens.

So in the virtual world text with work, students the most important information remembering to stay and learn daily in life in use help gives. These for and separately preparation demand will be done.

Preparation from the forms one this literary This activity is a journey. type from opportunities nature to the image dedicated or various factories, cities, villages, professions related topics and historical works when studied use to the goal according to. Literary excursions in the text reflection reached events more precisely imagination to reach, to the surrounding area realities to observe help gives. Adults labor activity, historical events perception to reach service does.

From the movie sheet demonstration to do Historical materials, work author his life from learning before such shaped approaches if used, the work deeper perception to be done increases. For example, general education In the 7th grade of schools, Abdulla Qodiriy's "From the Altar" "Scorpion" novel while dying from the movie fragment demonstration if done, from a movie taken personnel students imagination world to expand, concepts content to determine, conscious reading and emotional perception to grow skill formation

opportunity expands . Preparation their work this in a way organization to grow of the students education to receive and read was interests to increase will help .

The teacher 's storytelling . This approach importance work author about information in giving is known . The work author about speaking when given their portraits , children for wrote works demonstration If done , students author to his/her creativity relatively interests increases . Author by passed away works or they about other of the creators said audio form of the words putting The teacher also broadcasts to the story in harmony efficiency For example , in the 5th grade, A. Oripov's poem " Uzbekistan " in passing author's himself/herself studied from video footage use possible will be .

Teacher the material students age and level suitable without if you tell a story students artistic to the work relatively internal need exceed goes . The work to winter preparation work , as well as independent affairs also on the road Independent to research in direction to students in advance learnable topics according to of tasks giving is to be put .

Work content with introduction Preparation from the era next in stages work content with introduction works done In this process of the work one whole without perception also the text emotional the impact increase for the purpose him/her expressive winter separately place The work text with introduction one how much methods available . These are of the following consists of :

1. Text teacher by expressive readability . Some in cases text audio recording It is also available in the form of . Text content with After being introduced , the students work on the surface initial impressions with sharing is asked . For example , " The story which videos to you acceptable " What happened ? " , " From the heroes " which one to you more " Did you like it ?" , " The work reading at the time , especially at which places you happy did ?" like questions through work to them how impact what he did knowing to take possible . The work to be mastered circle entrance conversations , first of all , with students to their feelings the impact to know , secondly and the work text analysis to do interest , in class their activity increase to the goal service does .
2. Text speech fluent to the students teaching . In this teacher in advance to the student how reading necessity on the surface concept gives , its to read observed , mistakes and shortcomings to point out and correct help gives . Punctuation punctuation marks , stress , pause , intonation , articulation , diction such as speech technique about knowledge strengthens . From this then class to the team the text read to give possible will be .
3. Mouth again telling a story , speaking to give Such activity type separately preparation demand will , because the work to the text approaching storytelling to oneself typical requirements There are . In particular , in the work artistic image tools complete saved without storytelling necessary , because, artistic the work to study was interest weakening possible . D.Tashkhojeva to the mind According to , "Child text content to speak ready at the level speech to skill has since then story to do with forward and backward again story to do "It will be passed . "
4. From memory expressive winter Poetic works iodine to say through if delivered , this to the student positive impact shows . Also memorize in O'zide interest This is especially true for the teacher . sample separately place holds .
5. The work important dialogical their places or whole the work staging through introduction Such work type special preparation demand will . That is characters speech on to work , to

stage appearances and characters external appearances on top certain work integral without take to go through student in imagination of the work whole content to open help gives .

6. The work known one part , that is more problematic the plate teacher 's himself/herself read to give . In this to the students of the work remaining part themselves inside independent study task is assigned .

7. Technician from tools use . The work certain to the part prepared audio or video recordings in the form of text content delivered .

8. In harmony with music study . Such approach of the work impressionability to ensure that students aesthetic tastes to grow help gives . The most importantly , they from fatigue , mental from stress keeps .

Artistic work text on work three in stages done These are :

First stage synthesis period is calculated , its main task text content whole perception to grow through of the work content and imagery expressive tools with from introduction consists of .

Second stage analysis stage to be , to be task subject development mutual dependence identification , heroes character , temperament features determination is considered . In this of heroes why so road to hold reasons , this aspects in it which features open gives ; work composition node , culmination point , solution ; work content content to open service did figurative tools with together analysis to do and heroes character , attitudes price give ; author idea , direction , skill about information from mastering organization finds .

Third stage second synthesis stage is counted , in this work content of heroes important adjectives generalization , comparison , evaluation , work the idea to determine , its life knowledge and art work as instead to understand teaches . Second from synthesis then read done artistic to the work related without creative in content independent affairs is held .

Text on work and virtual world through travel to do , to students artistic of works content deeper in understanding help This approach gives of the students independent thinking , creativity and analysis to do skills to develop big contribution Addictive . Virtual world interactive from the means use , students new opportunities create and read process further effective does .

Used literature:

1. Yu'ldoshev Q., Qosimov B., Qodirov V. , Yu'ldoshbekov J. Literature : General middle education for 7th grade of schools textbook-complex . Repeat Revised 4th edition. – Tashkent: Sharq , 2017. 369 p.
2. Ahmedov , S. et al . General middle education 5th grade of schools for textbook . Tashkent: Teacher , 2020. 272 p.
3. Toshkhozhaeva D. R. Methodological foundations of teaching to retell the content of the text in one's own words (on the example of schools where education is conducted in Russian): Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences ...dissertation - T.: UzPFITI, 2000. - 102 p

